

**SERVICE DIGITALIZATION AND WORKERS EFFICIENCY IN NAVY REFERRAL
HOSPITAL, CALABAR C.R.S NIGERIA.**

By

¹Echadu, Melford Ochang; ²Dubu Museh Danbeki; ³Eyo Etim Akpadem; ⁴Ikaka,
Beconson Fredrick; ⁵Ogar, Victor Eyare

¹Department of Public Administration, University of Calabar, echadumelford@gmail.com

08063571290. Corresponding author

²Department of Public Administration, Federal University Wukari, Taraba Stat,,

dubu.museh82@gmail.com 07061016188

³Department of Public Administration, University of Calaba,

Eyoakpadem6@gmail.com 08064358424

⁴Department of Public Administration, University of

Calabar, beconsonfredrick@gmail.com, 081470226602

⁵Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education University of Calabar,

Victor.e.ogar@gmail.com 08176534589

ABSTRACT

The study examined the impact of service digitalization on employee's efficiency in Navy Referral Hospital Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria. Two specific objectives were examined in the study. An Ex post facto research design was adopted; a close ended questionnaire was used, and a sample of 150 respondents was drawn from the population. The questionnaire has section; A and B, section A deal with information on personal data, while section B examined the main variables of the study, which contained a total of 10 items? The data collected was tested using simple percentage and Chi Square statistical techniques was employed to analyze the data at 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom=2. The findings showed that: the introduction of electronic result administration tends to significantly improve employee's efficiency in patients result collation and that the introduction of e-transact in medical bills payment tends to have significantly improved employee's service delivery and reduced human errors. Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made there should be regular training especially in information communication (ICT) to improve staff technical potentials, and more technical equipment should be provided to make the work easy in order to reduce human errors and unnecessary bureaucratic delays; there should be regular replacement of faulty machines to avoid machine errors; and the management should ensure that physical cash are not collected from patients for proper accountability and effective records management. Conclusively, the integration of digital tools in Navy hospital, Calabar has improved service delivery though still challenged with effective training and infrastructure needs.

Keywords: Digitalization, Employee, Efficiency, Service

INTRODUCTION

Nothing is permanent in life other than the concept of change. Today, we are in a digital and computerized world such that technology is the order of the day. As such, every organization as well as offices are trying their best not to be left behind by upgrading their workers and services digitally to ensure efficiency of service delivery among staff, and many healthcare facilities are also in the forefront of this technological adventure. The Nigeria Navy Hospital, Calabar has been identified as one of the hospitals thriving technologically in their service delivery with outstanding human capital development. (Pena-casa et, al 2018)

Digitalization of healthcare is rapidly observed as a transformative force for the advancement of hospital, service delivery and staff efficiency such as electronic health records, and digital platform for most service delivery in health care, health-information system, streamline clinical workflows, enhance effective communication, reduction in manual operations to improved service digitalization (Hussein, 2025). Overtime, health care workers were often overstretched with the manual style of operation which the advent of digitalization in most service delivery has made the services faster and more efficient (Jeilani & Hussein). Empirical research in African hospitals underscores the positive impact of digitalization adaptation on health employee's performance, such as

Nigeria and South Africa indicating that healthcare with digital system is far more efficient, and Navy Hospital in Cross River is not an exceptional (Anusi & Mutambara, 2022)

Service digitalization in health care refers to the transformation of the health sector to a sophisticated standard with the necessary technical facilities that make work faster and encouraging such as electronic health records, telemedicine and teleconsultation, electronic test result administration, electronic bill payment and hospital information system. According Bhardwaj, et, al (2013), digitalization can enhance the efficacy services delivery with less human errors and bureaucratic bottle neck. The dramatic irony is that staff who are adapted to the analogue or manual style of doing things always find it difficult to meet up with the new system.

Efficiency in hospital refers to the enhanced capacity of the health employees to deliver standards services with optimal used of time, skills and resources while maintaining quality, timeliness, and patient satisfaction. It can further be describing as job performance compasses tasks such as technical and clinical tasks, contextual performance behavior that back up organizational activities and social environment, which includes cooperation and communication, adaptive performance (ability to adjust and response to changing demands).

Efficiency is the process where the medical personnel are able to provide proper and excellence service for the survival of patients (Krijgsheld et al, 2022).

As opined by Janna et, al, (2018), employee efficiency in hospital is a significant part that cannot be undermined due to vital services provided by the staff. Digitalization on the other hand can significantly impact on employee efficiency through automating administrative and technical tasks. It can also enhance a better clinical decision-making process, and streamlining communication. Employee efficiency metrics is seen as another major component of service efficiency because it involves how work can be perfectly done with cost effectiveness, improved access to information and time management.

Efficiency also known as technical and productivity improvement is often measured using health-facility outputs such as outpatient's patient visits, deliveries vaccinations, and number of health workers for their timely services. (Hasan et al, 2021). Similarly, (Krijgsheld et al, 2022) viewed employees' efficiency in hospital as effectiveness, timely, competence, and resource-savvy execution of clinical and non-clinical tasks with supportive organizational attitudes, adaptability to change, and critical avoidance to counter-productive behavior, resulting in optimal patient condition, efficient resources use and sustainable service delivery

Digitalization and technological advancements have significantly changed the way activities are carried out in the society, business functions and processes most especially at the hospital level. The dynamism in the corporate organizations and medical system has impacted individual functions in a number of ways. Hence, information technology influences the potential for enhancement even in business areas that traditionally have little to do with information technology (Chou. et. Al, 2014)

Nowadays, organizations are dealing with large amount of data, not only for informed decision making but also for their day-to-day activity. In order to handle large volumes of data, from different sources without compromise, organizations need to figure out how to manage big data to their advantages. Embracing the advantages of big data is not enough because in order to face the challenges of the business environment, investing in digital technology is no longer seen as a competitive advantage; but as a standard. Within the work environment, employees are now required to perform on a wider range of functions with technologies traditionally associated with their roles. If handled well, the impact digitalization has on employee's performance will create a positive contribution towards work flow and the prospects of enhanced services delivery. Technological shortcomings have a direct effect on work as working infrastructure is a prerequisite for productivity. Hence the need for this

study (Anamarija, et, al. 2019)

In spite of the numerous benefits associated with digitalization in Nigeria healthcare facilities such as Navy Referral Hospital, Calabar, they have also been significantly challenged by so many factors such as, poor test result administration, poor financial records management, inadequate infrastructure, fragmented approach to health care, inadequate trained personnel and poor power supply. In address, the above issue on service digitalization and employee's efficiency, management of healthcare organization and government should be able to provide the necessary facilities that will aid improved services delivery.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Though Navy Hospital Calabar have been trying their best to provide efficient services to her clients, these services were not very effective and efficient. It therefore, become pertinent to adopt digitalization to improve service delivery. However, this required technological innovations and strong organizational structures to enhance employees' performance, as they need to be to kept abreast with development and changes that constantly evolve in the work environment.

Contemporary organizations including the educational sector across the world has embraced technologies in

discharging job responsibilities which has prompted organizations to train their staffs on various technological tools with the aim of gaining higher productivity and performance from the work force. Gibbs (2017) recognizing that technology and innovation such as ICT are significantly relevant to the advancement of organizational goals.

Healthcare services digitalization is expected to promote adequate workflow efficiency and employee performance, but persistent changes in adoption and the utilization of modern technologies has constrained the effectiveness and efficiency of service delivery (Jeillani & Hussein, 2025) as Nigeria healthcare still struggle with poor and dilapidated medical facilities in the discharge of their official responsibilities. This has resulted to a high level of decline in providing their services efficiently (Babatope et al,2024)

Navy Hospital Calabar as a health institution has keyed into this global best practice of embracing technologies in the area of admission, receipts, bills payment among others as traditional approaches in handling job performance in the hospital in recent time has not improved the performance of employees prompting the hospital to adopt some technological strategies. Despite this, the hospital is still witnessing poor staff performance in handling job responsibilities. For instance, the issues of result administration have been seriously challenged even when hospital migrated from manual to electronic result access,

there are still cases of poor patient movement because the hospital admission unit have not been able to effectively handle patient's movement around wards in the hospital.

Recently, the hospital faced the issues of medical bills racketeering where people manipulate the hospital data base to issue fraudulent receipts to students. Though the hospital has trained personnel's on how best to use digitalization to curb the observed loopholes, how these technological applications and devices have impacted staff performance and enhanced their service delivery has remained the big question. Against this background, the following research question were formulated to guide the study.

- **Research questions**

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

- How has the introduction of electronic test result administration improved employees' efficiency?
- How has the introduction of electronic transacts improve employees' efficiency?

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

The broad objective of the study is to examine the impact of service digitalization on employees' efficiency in the Navy Hospital Calabar.

Specifically, the study sought to:

- Examine if the introduction of

electronic test result administration has improved staff efficiency in Navy hospital Calabar

- Investigate if the introduction of e-transact medical bills payment has improved staff efficiency in Navy hospital Calabar.

- **Statement of hypotheses**

- The introduction of electronic test result administration has significantly improved employee's efficiency Navy hospital, Calabar
- The introduction of e-transact in medical bills payment has significantly improved employee's efficiency in Navy hospital, Calabar

- **Significance of study**

Significantly, the study could guide policy maker within the ministry of health and all health personnel in all Navy hospital in the state to improve on their services to patients on how best to apply information communication technology (ICT) in handling of job responsibility which in turn will boost employee's performance. The findings and recommendation of this study will contribute and explains what will happen when information communication technology (ICT) is adopted and strategically employed by

doctors, nurses and non-medical staff of all health facilities in the state. It will reflect a suitable mechanism of boosting the effectiveness and efficiency of employees in an organization and the overall Performance of the organization.

The study would benefit employees and owners of health facilities by enabling them learn more about service digitalization on employee's efficiency. The study would contribute to new and existing knowledge on medical research as well as inspire investigations on similar area of study. The theory utilized could also serve as a guide to fill the gap on the impact of digitalization in hospital settings, especially in developing country.

- **Scope of the study**

Service digitalization on employee's efficiency research was delimited in Navy Referral Hospital, Calabar. It did not aim to review all the aspect involved in digitalization but focused mainly on the role of digitalization on employees' efficiency in areas such as electronic result administration, introduction of electronic transaction in medical fees payment and electronic receipts.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

- **Digitalization in Nigeria**

Digitalization is the socio-technical process of using digital technologies to maintain new changes in the society. It is a dynamic process which involves how a system can be re-structured and

upgraded, often facilitated by the combination of technologies, ICT and AI etc. (Brenneen and Kreiss, 2016; Franzel-piasentin et al, 2021). According to kan (2016), digital transformation is the most relevant term incorporating large-scale system, and cultural change that an organization undergoes as a result of adopting and integrating digital technological activities. Digitalization can also be extended to new revenue streams, driving the organizational custom experience and improved operational efficiency of service (Clerck, 2017; Honeywell, 2023)

Digitalization can also be described as the process whereby health care services, workflows, data management and patients' interactions are transformed from paper-based or manual processing to digital formats With the utilization of information communication technologies (ICT) and other forms of electronical health devices, such as medical health records system, digital referral systems, tele-medicine, remote monitoring equipment, online appointment booking, electronic prescription, digital billing system, and other ICT interventional materials (Kaihlänen et al, 2023)

In addition to the above contribution, digitalization as a socio-technical phenomenon is argued by many scholars as not purely technological issues but a socio- technical phenomenon (Frenzel-Piasentin et, al 2021). This implies that in digitalization, one thing is for the hospital to have the technological facilities and another thing

is for the hospital to have technical expert to operate the facilities as both cannot be separated if efficient services delivery is desired. Similarly, Bayhaqi et al, (2025) viewed digitalization as the innovativeness of an organization in services, such as electronic records management, telehealth system, mobile technologies and the effective utilization of such facilities to positively improves the quality of service delivery especially in healthcare centers. The cardinal objective of digitalization is therefore to provide easy access to service delivery, transparency, accountability and efficiency

- **Efficiency in Hospital**

The word efficiency implies the ability to produce a desire outcome through service delivery. According to Fuad, (2025) and Ananins, et al, (2024), efficiency is the capacity to produce the maximum possible result. It is based on the physical relationship between resource, technical services and outcome. An organization can be regarded as efficient if they are able to produce the same outcome with less input. Similarly, the concept of efficiency is concerns with the use of inputs in optimal proportions relatively on service delivery. In allocative efficiency resource are allocated to produce the goods and services that are seen very importance to clients

Efficiency in health care entails the level to which healthcare personnel professionally fulfil their tasks effectively and efficiently, and reliably. It

includes technical/service delivery tasks for instance, diagnosis, treatment, record management, timely test result, and non-technical /supports tasks such as communication, coordination, teamwork, administrative duties. It is often influenced by the availability and quality of digital equipment, effective in-service training, conducive organizational environment and workload management (Jeilani & Hessein,2925; Anusi & Mutambara,2022; Ajayi, et al 2022)

Efficiency is also described as a technical and productivity dimension, which can be measured from the day-day health services of outputs. (eg- out patient visits, how timely was the patient attended to before leaving the hospital. Was the patient satisfy with the treatment? Answering the above question remain the best ways to optimal efficiency in office. It provides the technical insight into employee's competencies and effective performance. (Hasan et al, 2021) Similarly, employees' efficiency is critically influenced by institutional supports and human resource practices such as employees training, employee's welfare, engagement and supportive administration, which directly influence employee's performance, collaboration, and effective resource utilization (Ngihejirika, Agbor & Nnabuchi, 2025)

Health care efficiency is very crucial because it help in allocating scare resource in order to meet the advancement and growing demands of

healthcare activities. Decision maker in health care always prioritize efficiency in their course of service delivery to ensure effective utilization of resource allocation. Similarly, efficiency can also be viewed in a technical dimension as the optimal production of good and services. It is the ability of health care personnel to ensure that professional service has being rendered to patients. When the organization is efficient in their service delivery, a lot of errors will be reduced both technical and manually.

-

- **Service Delivery.**

This is seen as a complex system of interrelated elements that ensure patients receive timely, effective and efficient care of treatment while also satisfying their needs and expectations. According Harriet et, al, 2024), service delivery is seen as a contractual transaction between a patient and the hospital. This implies that the health care provider capacity to be responsive to patient need most especially during emergencies ensuring that service are provided at the right time, effectively, efficiently to reduce the unnecessary delays (Okafor et, al, 2022) In addition to the above concepts, the World Health Organization indicated that service delivery is the provision and standard of making health care service affordable and available to all the clients (IGI Global, 2024). Quality service delivery and responsiveness entails the all components relate to the method of care provided by the health care system

and the capacity to respond to their needs. This implies that the level of service is very important because high quality service is linked to better patient satisfaction and positive result that further reduce delays that can result to poor and unhealthy healthcare. (Al-Damen, 2017; Rahman et, al 2017).

- **Electronic Test Result Administration**

Electronic test result administration refers to the digital way of managing, disseminating and displaying diagnostic test result, such as laboratory and radiology reports within the same hospital information system. The method is able to ensure timely delivery, accuracy of patient's information by the health provider. According to AHRO (2025), electronic test result is the process of making results available to patients through a secure portal as soon as the result is ready. Scholars also have it that the effectiveness of this administration critical depends on the overall functionality of the EHR (World Advanced Research and reviews,2024)

Electronic test-results administration in hospitals are digital laboratory results management described as subset service digitalization. It involves the application of electronic laboratory information system to record, process, store, retrieve and communicate diagnostic test or images results (blood test, x-rays, scan, lab analyses) digitally rather than via paper/ manual. This process ensure faster access to result, reduces errors in transcription or loss of paper results, enhance timely decision-making and enables integration with patients' electronic records through improved clinical workflow and effective coordination, and ultimately quality of care. It is also the process where result is no longer being administered hand to hand in paper interpretation but through

a machine that is capable of conducting the test and ability to interpret the result and transfer it electronically to the destination (kaihlansen et al, 2023),

Electronic test result is thus a process of using information technology to facilitate automated result notifications to clinicians which help in the prevention of missing result, delay and wrong result. (Akwaowo et, al 2022). Electronic test result is viewed as the capacity to enhance clinical efficiency, allowing quick access to a patient medical history, including the past, present and future lab results. It helps in providing a fast notification of result electronically to the clinician in making decision and advancement of further treatment. The objective is to provide healthcare provider with authentic and relevant information.

- **Electronic transacts processing and staff efficiency**

Electronic payment system is a means of making transaction through an e-network, that help an individual to pay for product or goods and services online. It required the use of financial machines and subscription of data. (Zou et, al, 2020). In a hospital system one can easily make payment for services through the use of patient portal or mobile phone. This method has also reduced high level of fraudulent activities from many cashiers and accountants. The automation has also reduced manual errors and delay in payment mode (Simbo, 2024)

- **E-payment platform**

This is an electronic medical bill payment in hospital which refers to digitalization of the billing and payment process, that allows patients/ guardians to receive, review and pay money or bills for lab test and other form of medical payment respectively for the services provided electronically, rather than manual transaction of cash. This digital billing payment system integrates with hospital financial and management systems tracking of services rendered, reduce billing errors, improve transparency, and facilitate enhanced revenue collection and records management. Electronic medical bill payment is therefore the financial digitalization of payment mode adopted in health sector to ease payment for patients and staff (Azizi 2024). According to Kaihlannen et al, (2023), e-payment transacts are financial transactions that take place with helps of electronic device that enhance quality financial transparency, including record keeping and report making. It is the general shift toward digital service delivery.

Electronic payment has really improved the financial activities of Navy hospital and also reduced the excess workload of many cashiers and accountant because of the convenient payment methods. It is more efficient and payment is backed up with receipts as payment evidence for records keeping. Hence, any system used for managing medical records is referred to as

receipts system. A receipts system is a patient's information management system for processing and managing patients' medical information. Dennis (2004) thus defined e-payment system as a form of financial commitment that involves the buyer and the seller facilitated via the use of electronic communications while Briggs and Brooks (2011) reported e-payment as a form of inter-connections between organizations and individuals aided by banks and inter-switch houses that enables monetary exchange electronically.

- **Empirical Review**

Okoro & Orjiako (2025) conducted a study on office information systems and service-delivery efficiency in federal universities in Nigeria namely UNN, FUT0, NAU, Alex Ekwueme, Micheal Okpara. The study employed descriptive survey design with a population of 118 senior administrative staff officers. Census sampling was adopted, Delone and Mclean Information Acceptance Model was utilized as a lens for the study. The study was constraints by cross-sectional (no longitudinal change) as it was limited to Registry officers. Key findings revealed that high integration; user competence significantly improved service-delivery efficiency. The study also recommended that the ICT should be strengthen with adequate digital infrastructures and regular training

Gbenga et al, (2025) conducted a study on digitalization and performance of

service sector at a service firm, Calabar, Nigeria. The study employed qualitative descriptive design with the sector firm employees. Key findings of the study revealed that internet adoption, social network performance, mobile tech positively influenced employees service performance. The study was also constrained by limited test on employee's efficiency. Based on the findings the study recommended that a more rational focus on employees training and digital networking to improve decision making process and service outputs.

Olayinka-Agboola et al, (2025) also conducted a study on the impact of digitalization on public service in Nigeria, a case study of Federal civil service in Nigeria. The study adopted quantitative method survey, with sample size of 369 from a targeted of 575 of the respondents. The study adopted a stratified random sampling technique. The study findings revealed that digitalization significantly influence service delivery and efficiency with the umbrella of transparency and accountability. Based on the study, it was recommended that government should invest in digital infrastructure to enhance effective communication to support, public service efficiency

Omofowa & Ogbonmwan (2025) similarly conducted a study on digitalization of work practices and its impact on employee's engagement in Nigeria Manufacturing Sector at Edo state manufacturing industries, Nigeria. The study adopted cross-sectional

survey methods with a sample size of 300 from the employees' firm. The study utilized demands-resources model. Key findings reveal that digital productivity processes, job autonomy, and satisfaction positively enhance effective engagement at workplace. Based on the findings, the study recommended that upskilling, supportive leadership and robust infrastructure to sustain dedication.

- **Theoretical framework**
 - ▶ **Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) 1986**

Technology acceptance model was propounded by Fred Davis in his doctoral dissertation at Massachusetts Institute of Technology. He believes that personal decision to use technological instrument is highly motivated by their beliefs about the technology. This implies that technological activities are determined by the user behavior and perception. The theory further explained the perceived usefulness which refers to an extent to which a person strongly believes that using a particular system will enhance effective job performance. This implies that if the user believe that the technology is beneficial to them in undergoing a task, they are likely be interested in using it.

The model categorically states that perceived ease of the uses is highly significant. This refers to the degree to which a person believes that the utilization of a particular technology will

be stress less and from many challenges. This also implies that the easier a technology is to learn and use, the more competent the user become. Perceived ease also advocate the direct influence of technological advancement in the society. It explained that the more you use technology, you will become knowledgeable and adopted to it and this can help in shaping the attitude to the utilization of technology.

► **Tenets of the theory.**

1. **The beliefs of drive behavior:** This explained how user attitudes toward technology are fundamentally shaped by their beliefs about the usefulness and ease of the technology.

2. **The priority of usefulness:** The theory further explained that the user is more prepared to adopt to a technology when they believe it will improve and positively contribute to their overall performance.

3 **Ease of the use reduce many challenges:** This implies that the usefulness of technology may be rejected if it is concluded as too difficult to use, the simpler the technology is, the easier it is and less resistance.

► **Application**

In Navy Referral Hospital Calabar, the process of implementing new health information system such as electronic health records, mobile health records and e-test result administration is very challenges because not all medical personnel are ready for the adaptation. However, electronic health care help to

increase perceived usefulness It will reduce many medical errors, streamline workflow and enable staff maintain a good database.

The TAM can also serve as a telemedicine platform where Navy hospital will want to use a new telemedicine platform for remote consultations and training for potential medical personnel as an effective guide. Perceived ease of use is viewed as where a simple set up and use for both clinician and patients. It should be user friendly and interface with clear instruction for digital and technical service such as video call, securing messages and vital data for future utilization. Hopefully, Navy hospital will do better and can proactively address many medical barriers to technology adoption by ensuring that the new system is effectively implemented and good follow-up of health education to staff and patients

► **Gap in literature**

There are many kinds of research gap but for this study, it is delimited to geographical scope and further extended to methodology which adopted the use of quantitative data. Existing study focuses mainly on civilian public hospital leaving military/Navy referral hospital understudied while many scholars adopted qualitative approach. There is limited evidence on workers adaptation efforts, workload changes, or digital skill development in such setting. Studies appeals for long-term system performance and

evaluation.

METHODOLOGY

- **Research design**

The study adopted an expo facto research design. This design would enhance a better picture, features, and construct statistical tools in explaining what is observed. It served as an enabler to explain how one variable (digitalization) impacts on the other (workers performance). As (Umans 2018) depicted that "results on employees could be linked to the featured of the working environment, which must change in the same proportion as the organization transforms. Also, previous research has shown that an appropriate environment positively affects workers' productivity and behaviour.

- **Research Area**

This study was conducted in Navy Referral Hospital Calabar in Cross River State. The Navy Hospital Calabar is located along the high way in the municipal region of Cross River State, Nigeria and it was established in the year 2018. It has 20 departments and well over 600 staff to its credits. In the midst of several departments in the hospital, this study will take particular references to the nursing unit with all the caregivers inclusive. Administratively, the city is divided into Calabar Municipal and Calabar South LGAs.

- **Population of the study**

Population is seen as the total collection of objects, subjects or participants with a mutual description. It can also be referred to the collection of people in an area, sharing a particular characteristic of interest most often that of living in a given area. It is also a group of units (persons, objects, or other items) enumerated in a census or from which a sample is drawn. The study population is 600 staff. The population for this study comprised the staff of Navy Referral Hospital, Calabar.

- **Sampling techniques**

The sampling technique adopted for this study is stratified technique. It was considered appropriate by the researcher because it enable the researcher to randomly assign equal numbers of respondents to each stratum under study. The sample was drawn from, difference departments, units, cadres, such as Doctors, Nurses and administrative personnel from Navy Referral Hospital Calabar.

- **Sampling size**

This reflects the selection of a number of units from the defined population of study. Therefore, the sample size of this study consists of 150 respondents derived from the three strata under study. They include 50 doctors, 50 nurses and 50 non-medical personnel. The instrument of data collection is the administration of questionnaire. Each item in the questionnaire was developed to address specific objectives of the

study. Questionnaires were used because they are convenient tools where there are a large number of subjects to be handled. They facilitated easy and quick derivation of information.

- **Sources of data collection**

For the purpose of this study, data were collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary and secondary sources of information served as a veritable tool for data collection. Sources of data collection was on a first-hand basis through questionnaire. Secondary data were collected from research reports, textbooks, journals, papers and other published as well as unpublished materials of relevance to the study and internet websites.

- **Validity of the instrument**

Validity refers to the accuracy and meaningfulness of inferences, which are based on the research results. Validity is the degree to which results obtained from the analysis of the data actually represents the phenomenon under study. The validity therefore has to do with how accurately the data obtained in the study represents the variables of the study. Therefore, a draft of the research instruments (Questionnaires) were submitted to experts for review and approval. This included analysis of the items of the instrument, modified some items before approval was given to use the instrumentation for the study. With this, the instrument was regarded as valid.

- **Reliability of the instrument**

Reliability is the degree in which research instrument is consisted and dependable in producing accurate result. As a result of this, 20 questionnaires were distributed and collected back within two weeks and the result seem to be the same and reliable

- **Data analysis techniques**

There are several statistical techniques that are used in research to test the level of significance or impact between variables. Due to the involvement of different variables, the chi square statistical technique was adopted for testing hypothesis and analysis of data.

The chi square technique is also used to test the hypothesis for the difference between the set of observed frequencies and a corresponding expected frequency. The formula for chi square is stated below.

The formula for calculating chi-square is given as follows:

$$= \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where \sum = summation

O = observed variables

E = Expected variables

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

- **Data presentation**

A total of one hundred and fifty (150) copies of questionnaire were produced

and administered to respondents in Navy Referral Hospital Calabar with the aid of a research assistant. Out of the one hundred and fifty (150) copies of questionnaire distributed, one hundred and forty-five (145) copies were correctly filled and returned while five (5) copies were either not correctly filled or not returned to the researcher. Therefore, the one hundred and forty-five (145) copies that were correctly filled and returned were used as a basis of analysis of this study.

TABLE 1: Distribution of respondents based on gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage%
Male	80	55.2%
Female	65	44.8%
Total	145	100
Age		
18-27	27	18.69%
28-37	20	13.79%
38-47	33	22.8%
48-57	30	20.69%
58 and above	35	25.14%
Total	145	100
FLSC	32	21.2%
SSEC	16	10.67%
ND/NCE	40	30.67%
B.Sc.	32	16.4%

MBA/MA/M.Sc.	15	12.2%
/	10	
Ph.D.		7.67%
Total	145	100

The table above shows that a total of 145 respondents were represented 80 (55.2%) percent of the respondents were male while 65 (44.8%) respondents were females. The Table also represents the distribution of respondents based on age. It shows that 18.69% percent were within 18-27 age representing, 13.79 percent, were within the age bracket of 28-37, while 22.8 percent of the respondents, were within 38-47, and 48-57, respondents were within 20.69% level, also 58 and above were on the age bracket, within the range of 25.14% respectively. The educational qualifications of respondents also indicated that 32 (13.5%) of the respondents are FSLC holders, 16 (%) are SSCE holders, 40% are holders of OND and NCE, 32.5%) are BA, B.Sc. and HND holders, 15. (5%) hold M.Sc., and (10%) are PhD holders

- **Data analysis**

TABLE 2: The introduction of e-result data base has helped you to be more effective in medical result computations

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Strongly agree	122	84.1
Agree	4	2.8

Disagree	8	5.5
Strongly disagree	11	7.6
Total	145	100

TABLE 3: Error in patient's laboratory test results are now minimal because there are computed electrically

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Strongly agree	100	69
Agree	5	3.4
Disagree	20	13.8
Strongly disagree	20	13.8
Total	145	100

TABLE 4: Staff can now address result related issues faster than when it was manually computed

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Strongly agree	80	55.2
Agree	17	11.7
Disagree	25	17.2
Strongly disagree	23	15.9
Total	145	100

TABLE 5: Electronic results administration has helped you in

effective results record keeping

Response	Frequency	Percentage %
Strongly agree	54	37.2
Agree	38	26.2
Disagree	31	21.4
Strongly disagree	22	15.2
Total	145	100

• Test of hypotheses

Hypotheses 1

1. The introduction of electronic test result administration tends not to significantly improve employee's performance in patients result collation

TABLE 6: Chi-square analysis of introduction of electronic test result administration tends not to significantly improve employee's efficiency in patients result collation at .05

OPINION OF SUBJECT

Response	S	A	D	S	N	Cal	D	Crit
	A			D		x^2	f	X^2
	6	2	4	2	1	24	2	16.92
	0	0	0	5	4	4.1		
						5	06	

Significant at .05, df=2, t=61,41`

The decision rule of X state that if the calculated value of X is greater or less than table value at a given significance

level, we reject the null hypothesis. Since the calculated value of X^2 (244.106) is greater than table value of (16.92) we therefore reject the null hypothesis (H_0) i.e. out of the sample of 145 who responded to the questionnaire, their responses indicate that; introduction of electronic result administration significantly improve employee's performance in patients result collation.

- **Discussion of findings**
Hypotheses 1

The result of the research revealed that the introduction of electronic result administration has significantly improved employees' performance in patients result collation. The result of this research on hypotheses agrees with other findings. With the introduction of e-payment system, the world payment system leaned towards cashless transactions among individuals, businesses and governments, thus Akwaowo, (2022) opined that, the world payments system is gradually changing from coins and paper-based money to electronic forms that provide more convenient, fast and secured process of making payments among individual and organizations. AHRO (2025) opined that electronic test result is a process of making results available to patients through a secure portal as soon as the result is ready have attracted much attention from researchers and information system designers due to their vital role in modern electronic activities.

This led to wide and in-depth research that produced different perspectives on e-payment definitions among others. These definitions were mainly viewed from different perspectives ranging from scholars in the field of accounting and finance, business technology to those in information systems. For instance, Dennis (2004) defines e-payment system as a form of financial commitment that involves the buyer and the seller facilitated via the use of electronic communications. Also, Briggs and Brooks (2011) sees e-payment as a form of inter-connections between organizations and individuals aided by banks and inter-switch houses that enables monetary exchange electronically.

This research work examined the role of service digitalization on workers efficiency in the Navy Referral Hospital Calabar and revealed that the Navy Referral Hospital Calabar being a health institution has adopted various digitalized tools and procedures such as the electronic result payment transaction which has greatly promote the efficiency of workers and correction of mistakes.

CONCLUSION

It is obvious to say that digitalization has come to stay and serve as an instrument of transformation in today's world ranging from both individual, corporate and governmental parastatal. Research and journals of study have proven that job performance, effectiveness and efficiency,

organizational delivery has been on a maximum since the discovery or the employment of digital tools as it has been a global best practice. Health institutions worldwide have adopted this global best practice thereby boosting performance and satisfaction, organized and less stressful venture which relatively have created or served as a positive shift toward service delivery.

Navy Hospital Calabar has also adopted this practice ranging from receipts processing, result administration, and electronic transaction which relatively have created a boost in workers performance and their attitude towards work which leads to effective delivery. It is therefore, conclusively that digitalization is hospital enhance better service delivery and is more likely a requirement to for effective administration. It helps to curb crimes by fixing the level of patient's maltreatment and crime activities consisting of fees racketeering, missing of test results and unnecessary bureaucratic bottle net in the hospital.

Service digitalization in Navy Referral Hospital Calabar has positively promote employee's efficiency through effective workflow's administration, by improving information accessibility and reducing delay and multiple human errors. The integration of digitalization has also strengthened effective coordination across departments and improved the quality of service delivery. The study findings also revealed that staff need more training to readily adapt with the ever-changing technological trends.

• Recommendations

Based on the above findings, the following recommendations were made:

- ▶ There should be regular training especially in information communication (ICT) to improve staff potentials. This will build professional competencies among medical personnel and more technical equipment should be provided to make the work easier and reduce human errors and unnecessary bureaucratic delay
- ▶ There should be regular replacement of machines that are malfunctional fine to avoid machine errors and the management should ensure that physical cash should not be collected by officers or from patients to enhance proper accountability and effective records management

• Limitation of the study

In the course of this study, the research work was constraint in many areas such as finances, poor attitude of respondents, limited time frame and poor power supply system.

REFERENCES

- AHRQ (2025). Diagnostic issue brief 19 electronic test result communication in the era of 21th

- century Cures Act: *Agency for healthcare research and quality.*
- Akwaowo, E. U. (2022). Benefits and challenges of adopting electronic medical records in Nigeria Federal Capital Territory Hospitals.
- AL-Damen, R. (2017). Service quality and patient satisfaction in Jordanian hospitals. *International journal of health care quality assurance*, 30(2),173-186
- Anamarija Cijan, Lea Jenic, Amadeja Lamovsek and Jakob Stemberger (2019). How digitalization changes the workplace. *Dynamic Relationships Management Journal*, (8)1.
- Ananins, I. & Spraka, M. (2024). Efficiency, effectiveness and efficacy in health care:
- Anusi, I. H., & Mutambara, E. (2022). Digital Technology and Health Workers' Performance: A Case of Hospitals in Nigeria and South Africa. *International Journal of Social Science and Religion*, 3(3). <https://doi.org/10.53639/ijssr.v3i3.118>
- Brennen, J. S. & Kreiss, D. (2016). Digitalization and digital transformation: Definitions frameworks and research agenda. *Journal of communication*.
- Chesley, N. (2010). Technology use and employee assessments of work effectiveness, workload, and pace of life. *Information, communication & society.*
- Chou, Y.-C, Chuang, H. H. C. and Shao, B. B. M. (2014) "The impacts of information technology on total factor productivity: A look at externalities and innovations", *International Journal of Production Economics*.
- Clerk, T. (2017). The use of digital technologies and data in order to create revenue: *Journal of innovation management*
- Collin J., Halen, M., Helenius M., Hiekkanen K., T., & Itala T., & Korhonen, J. J. (2014) IT leadership in Finnish organizations and digital transformation, TEKES final report, 2014.
- Fashoto, O. Y., Sibiya, M. N., & Oladimeji, O. (2025). Health workers' perception of digital technology use to improve mental health services. *Journal of Public Health in Africa*, 16(1), a1337. <https://doi.org/10.4102/jphia.v16i1.1337>
- Frenzel-piasentin, D, (2021), Distinguishing digitalization and digitization: A systematic review and conceptual framework.
- Fuad, A. M. Takia, N. A. Zafir, H. A. & Farrok, O. (2025), Enhancing operational efficiency through

- overall equipment efficiency optimization and kaizen initiatives. PLOS One, 20(5), e0320761
- research Centre, 1615 L St. NW, suite 800 Washington, DC 20036, USA
- Gbenga, L. S., Ubi, B. B., Phobuh, C. A., Obiora, E. P., Meyengue, T., Eventus, B. S., & Udo, N. E. (2025). Digitalization and performance of service sector. *Law and Economy*, 4(6), 22–32.
<https://doi.org/10.63593/LE.2788-7049.2025.07.003>
- Gibbs, M. (2017). How is new technology changing job design? IZA world of labour 2017.
- Harriet, G. (2024), Service delivery of health information management professionals. *International journal of library, information & communication sciences*, 2(1).
- Hasan, M. Z., et al. (2021). A practical measure of health facility efficiency: An innovation in the application of routine health information to determine health worker productivity. *Human Resources for Health*, 19, 96.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12960-021-00636-6>
- IGI Global (2024). The world health organization (WHO)Honeywell, (2023). What is digitalization? Honey well News.
- Janna Anderson & lee Raine (2018) "stories from the experts about the impact of digital life" pew
- Jeilani, A., & Hussein, A. (2025). Impact of digital health technologies adoption on healthcare workers' performance and workload: perspective with DOI and TOE models. *BMC Health Services Research*, 25, 271.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-025-12414-4>
- Jimoh, T. A., & Jimoh, I. B. (2024). Exploring the influence of digital technology on administrative service delivery in tertiary institutions: An empirical insight from The Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(11), 316–326.
<https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2024.8110026>
- Kane, G. C. palmer, D. Philips, A. N. Kiron, D. & Buckley (2017) Strategy, not technology, drives digital transformation. MIT Sloan management review
- Krijgsheld, M., Tummers, L., & Scheepers, F. (2022). Job performance in healthcare: A systematic review. *BMC Health Services Research*, 22(1), 149.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-021-07357-5>

- Kumi, E., Appiah, T., & Dartey-Baah, K. (2025). The impact of digital transformation on organisational dynamics, HR practices, and wellbeing in Ghana's healthcare sector: a social exchange perspective. *Future Business Journal*, 11, 64.
- Kusisto M. (2015). Effects of digitalization on organization. Master of Science thesis; Tampere Hospital of technology.
- Menezes, L. M., & Escrig-Tena, A. B. (2023). Performance measurement systems in the health and care sector: Are targets and monitoring additional demands or resources for employees? *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOPM-12-2022-0763>
- Mensah, N. K., et al. (2023). Perceived impact of digital health technology on health professionals and their work: a qualitative study in Southern Ghana. *Digital Health*.
- Nglhejirika, N. O., Agbo, I. C., & Nnabuchi, H. C. (2025). Human resources policies and employee performance: Evidence from Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital, Yaba, Lagos. *Applied Journal of Economics, Management and Social Sciences*, 5(3), 58-71.
<https://doi.org/10.53790/ajmss.v5i3.105>
- Okafor, et, al, (2022). Service delivery quality and service Performance of private hospitals in Calabar.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378177867>
- Okoro, B. O., & Orjiako, M. C. (2025). Office information systems and service-delivery efficiency in federal universities: Evidence from South-East Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, 12(10), 3812–3822.
<https://doi.org/10.51244/IJRSI.2025.1210000328>
- Olayinka-Agboola, M., Ismail, Y., & Eke, C. I. (2025). Impact of digitalization on public service delivery in Nigeria: A case study of Federal Civil Service in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Information Systems & Technology Research*, 13(2), 132–142.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15601615>
- Omofowa, M. S., & Ogbonmwan, O. (2025). Digitalization of work practices and its impact on employee engagement in Nigeria's manufacturing sector. *Kashere Journal of Management Sciences*, 8(2). Retrieved from
<https://journals.fukashere.edu.ng/index.php/kjms/article/view/892>
- Pena-casa R., Ghailani D. & Coster S. (2018). The impact of

- digitalization on job quality in European public services. The case of homecare and employment service workers. Final Report. European social observatory (OSE) and European public service union (EPSU).
- Simbo, A. (2024). Exploring the impact of innovative patient payment solution on hospitals revenue cycle management efficiency.
- Uzochukwu, I. U., Nwoye, M. I., & Azu, N. P. (2025). Effect of digital technology adoption on the performance of supervisory agencies of the Nigerian communications sector: Does behavioural intention matter? *International Journal of Innovative Research and Scientific Studies*, 8(7), 281–291. <https://doi.org/10.53894/ijirss.v8i7.10436>
- World Journal of advanced research and reviews (2024). Impact of electronic health records on patient care and outcomes: A comprehensive review
- Zidane, Y. & Olsson, S, (2017). A literature review on the effectiveness and efficiency of business model. DiVA portal.
- Zou, X. Wang, Q. L. (2020). A review on electronic payments security. MDPI